

EFFECT OF AUTOMATED ACCOUNTING SYSTEM ON THE CORPORATE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN SOUTH EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study examined the Effect of an Automated Accounting System on the corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to examine the effect of Information Technology Infrastructure on the corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria. evaluate the effect of Internal Controls on corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria. A descriptive research design was employed for the study. A questionnaire design with a five-point Likert scale was used to collect data for the study. The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive statistics (such as percentages and frequency distributions) and inferential statistics (notably Chi-square tests). The result revealed that Information Technology Infrastructure has a significant effect on the corporate financial performance, with a p-value ($0.001 < 0.05$). Internal Controls have a significant effect on the corporate financial performance, with a p-value ($0.001 < 0.05$) in South East Nigeria. The study concludes that the Automated Accounting System has a significant effect on the corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria. The study recommended that Organizations in South East Nigeria should prioritize investments in robust IT infrastructure. This includes upgrading hardware, software, and network systems to ensure seamless integration and operation of automated accounting systems.*

Keywords: Accounting, Automated, Financial, Performance, System

1.1 Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving business landscape, characterized by increasing complexity and the need for real-time insights, organizations are turning to automated accounting systems to streamline their financial operations (Kenton 2024). Accounting automation involves utilizing software and technology to perform routine accounting tasks, such as data entry, transaction recording, reconciliation, and financial reporting, with minimal human intervention (Fisher, 2023). These systems leverage advanced technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Robotic Process Automation (RPA), and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) to enhance efficiency, accuracy, and speed in managing financial processes (Chipriyanova & Krasteva-Hristova, 2023).

Automated accounting systems offer a stark contrast to traditional manual accounting methods, which rely heavily on human data entry, complex spreadsheets, and paper documents (Kenton 2024). Manual processes are not only time-consuming and labour-intensive but also prone to errors, limiting a company's visibility into its financial health and making it difficult to scale operations (Chipriyanova & Krasteva-Hristova, 2023). By automating repetitive tasks and providing real-time data, automated accounting systems free up accounting teams to focus on higher-level, strategic activities such as financial analysis, investment planning, and strategic decision-making (Huong, 2020).

The benefits of automated accounting systems are wide-ranging. They include increased efficiency and productivity, enhanced data accuracy, faster data retrieval, improved cash flow management, and better regulatory compliance (Fisher, 2023). By reducing the risk of human error and providing real-time access to financial data, these systems enable businesses to make more informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and achieve sustained growth and profitability (Fisher, 2023). As automation becomes the new standard in the finance industry, businesses that fail to adapt risk falling behind their competitors (Yulianti et al. 2024).

In South-East Nigeria, businesses are progressively adopting automated accounting systems to streamline their financial operations and enhance corporate financial performance. Several studies have highlighted the positive impact of automated accounting systems on financial performance. These studies suggest that the use of automated systems leads to better reporting, improved decision-making, more efficient resource utilization, and faster processing of financial data (Kenton 2024). Furthermore, the adoption of accounting software can improve the accuracy, timeliness, and reliability of financial information, which ultimately translates to better financial performance. Therefore, the transition to automated accounting systems is crucial for businesses in South-East Nigeria seeking to enhance their financial performance and maintain a competitive edge in today's dynamic business landscape.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The adoption of automated accounting systems (AAS) has become increasingly prevalent among businesses in South-East Nigeria as a response to the growing demands for efficiency and accuracy in financial management. However, the extent to which these systems impact corporate financial performance remains unclear. Despite the potential benefits of AAS—such as improved accuracy, reduced operational costs, and enhanced decision-making capabilities—many organizations still grapple with issues related to implementation, employee training, and system integration.

Moreover, there is limited empirical research specifically focused on the South-East Nigerian context, where cultural, economic, and infrastructural factors may influence the effectiveness of automated accounting systems. This gap in knowledge raises critical questions about the actual effects of AAS on key financial performance indicators such as profitability, revenue growth, and cost efficiency.

Consequently, businesses may be unable to fully leverage the advantages of automation, resulting in suboptimal financial outcomes.

This study seeks to investigate the relationship between automated accounting systems and corporate financial performance in South-East Nigeria, aiming to identify the challenges and benefits associated with AAS adoption. By addressing this gap, the research will provide valuable insights for businesses considering the transition to automated systems and contribute to the broader discourse on financial management practices in emerging economies.

1.3 Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the Effect of Automated Accounting System on the corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to;

- i. Examine the effect of Information Technology Infrastructure on the corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of Internal Controls on the corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria.

1.4 Hypotheses of the study

- i. Information Technology Infrastructure has no significant effect on the corporate financial performance in Southeast Nigeria.
- ii. Internal Controls has no significant effect on the corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Automated Accounting System

Automation Accounting System requires the application of software to computerize important financial functions of any organization. (Fisher, 2023). Automated accounting systems, also known as accounting software, leverage technology to automate various accounting functions, from data entry and bookkeeping to financial reporting and tax preparation. Imagine a world where invoice processing is instantaneous, reconciliation is effortless, and financial reports are generated with a single click. The digitization of accounting through automated systems is a response to the growing complexity of the global business environment. As businesses expand and financial regulations become more intricate, the demand for accurate, timely, and transparent accounting information has escalated. Automated accounting systems meet these demands by providing comprehensive and up-to-date financial reports, thereby enhancing decision-making processes and operational efficiency (Chipriyanova & Krasteva-Hristova, 2023).

The advent of automated accounting systems marks a pivotal shift in the accounting industry, heralding a technological revolution that has transformed traditional practices. This transformation is

underpinned by the integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and cloud computing, fundamentally altering the landscape of accounting and financial management (Amneh et al., 2020; Chipriyanova & Krasteva-Hristova, 2023). The emergence of these systems is not merely a technological upgrade but a comprehensive redefinition of how accounting processes are conceived, implemented, and managed. These systems leverage the power of AI and machine learning algorithms to analyze vast amounts of data, generating insights and forecasts that were previously unattainable with manual methods. The role of cloud computing in this revolution cannot be overstated, as it provides the necessary infrastructure for scalable, flexible, and secure accounting applications, facilitating remote access and real-time data processing (Huong, 2020).

Information Technology Infrastructure

Information technology infrastructure ITI is defined as the shared information technology resources consisting of a technical, physical base of hardware, software, communication technologies, data, core applications, human component skills and expertise combined to create quality services that are typically unique to an organization (Owusu, 2017). IT infrastructure consists of a set of physical devices and software applications that are required to operate the entire enterprise. But IT infrastructure is also a set of firm-wide services budgeted by management and comprising both human and technical capabilities (Mauerhoefer et al., 2017). Allameh et al. (2011) believed that achieving high efficiency and effectiveness in organizations requires investment in IT components, such as the Internet, office automation, and management information systems.

An IT infrastructure serves as the basis for computer technology, communications, and basic data systems, within the technical framework that guides organizational work to meet management needs. Mitchell et al. (2012) indicated that an IT infrastructure is the foundation upon which a firm can deliver reliable services through an organized and coordinated central information system. All organizations that rely on technology to do their business can benefit from having a robust, interconnected IT Infrastructure. With the current speed which technology changes and the competitive nature of businesses, IT leaders have to ensure that their IT Infrastructure is designed such that changes can be made quickly and without impacting business continuity. IT Infrastructure can be managed by the company itself or it can be outsourced to another company that has consulting expertise to develop robust infrastructures for an organization (Laan, 2011).

Internal Controls

Internal controls are accounting and auditing processes used in a company's finance department that ensure the integrity of financial reporting and regulatory compliance. Internal controls help companies to comply with laws and regulations and prevent fraud. They can also help improve operational efficiency by ensuring that budgets are adhered to, policies are followed, capital shortages are identified, and accurate reports are generated for leadership. Internal controls have become a key business

function for every U.S. company since the accounting scandals of the early 2000s (Kenton, 2024). Internal controls are broadly divided into preventive and detective activities. Preventative control activities aim to deter errors or fraud from happening in the first place and include thorough documentation and authorization practices. Detective controls are backup procedures that are designed to catch items or events that have been missed by the first line of defense.

No two systems of internal controls are identical, but many core philosophies regarding financial integrity and accounting practices have become standard management practices. While they can be expensive, properly implemented internal controls can help streamline operations and increase operational efficiency, in addition to preventing fraud (Kenton, 2024). The success of internal controls can be limited by personnel who cut control activities for the sake of operational efficiency and by those employees who work together to conceal fraud. Rezaee (2005) emphasizes that strong internal control systems reduce the likelihood of financial statement misstatements, whether due to fraud or error. Yulianti et al. (2024) demonstrated that robust internal control systems significantly contribute to reducing fraudulent activities in financial reporting. Spencer Stuart (2014) argues that internal control is a governance tool that helps board members and executive management meet their fiduciary duties. It assures that business activities are aligned with strategic objectives and regulatory expectations.

Corporate Financial Performance

Corporate Financial Performance (CFP) is a fundamental concept in finance, accounting, and strategic management, as it encapsulates the effectiveness of a firm's use of its assets to generate revenue and deliver value to stakeholders. It is a multidimensional construct, typically evaluated through a combination of accounting-based measures (e.g., return on assets [ROA], return on equity [ROE], net profit margin), market-based measures (e.g., stock price, market value added), and cash flow-based indicators. Corporate financial performance is rooted in several theoretical perspectives that explain how firms create value and sustain profitability. Several internal and external factors have been identified as determinants of CFP. Internally, corporate governance structures play a vital role. According to Yasser, Entebang, and Mansor (2011), board size, CEO duality, and the proportion of independent directors significantly influence financial performance.

Despite advancements in theory and measurement, assessing CFP remains fraught with challenges. One issue is the time lag between strategic initiatives and financial outcomes. Many performance measures are backward-looking and may not capture future profitability. Moreover, earnings management and accounting manipulation can distort reported performance. Measures that are relevant in one industry or geographic market may not be applicable in another. For instance, ROE benchmarks differ significantly between financial services and manufacturing sectors. Similarly, market-based measures are less informative in emerging markets where stock markets may be inefficient or illiquid (Friede, Busch, & Bassen, A., 2015).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Technology Acceptance Theory

The technology acceptance theory was proposed by Davis in 1989 (Davis, 1989) and was adapted from the theory of reasoned action. The technology acceptance theory is concerned with the general acceptance of information technology by society, the business community, workplaces, and researchers. It suggests that the world is witnessing new technological innovations, and the use of computers and the level of acceptance and application of technology in every human activity are impressive and a welcome tool for solving problems and getting things done speedily. Zhang et al. (2020) noted that technological innovations are widely accepted as a new way of life and have gradually affected every part of human beings, as the way of doing things globally now revolves around new technologies.

Dagilene and Kloviene (2019) noted that the acceptance of information technology has brought new ways of thinking, communicating, and doing business, and this has brought lots of economic gains to society. The theory suggests that development to optimize the flow of information to trigger knowledge to cope with growing business transactions and the level of acceptance of information systems have made a huge contribution to private and corporate organizations in enhancing strategic planning and meeting business objectives.

2.3 Empirical Reviews

Nada et al (2016) conducted a study to investigate the impact of information technology (IT) Infrastructure on Innovation performance as a critical issue in the Iraqi private Universities. The study aims to examine the direct effects of ITI components (hardware, software, network, and human resources) on innovation performance and assess the role of IT capability in enhancing institutional innovation in the Iraqi private Universities. The study utilized a descriptive-statistical design. The results revealed a positive and statistically significant association between IT Infrastructure and innovation performance.

Plotnikova & Rubanov (2020) conducted a study on the Role of Internal Control Systems (ICS) as a management function and a component of integrated financial reporting in selected firms in Russia. The study aims to investigate the functions and structure of internal control systems (ICS), analyze how ICS contributes to enhanced transparency, financial reliability, and management decision-making, and examine the integration of ICS into corporate reporting, particularly in the context of integrated financial statements in corporate organizations in Russia. The study employed a descriptive and analytical empirical study. The results revealed that Internal control systems are essential for effective corporate management and accountability.

Widajanti & Ratnawati (2020) conducted a study to explore and analyze the optimization of IT infrastructure in achieving performance-based innovation in companies in Indonesia. The study aims to investigate how the optimization of IT infrastructure contributes to innovation, examine the

influence of IT infrastructure components: hardware, software, networks, databases, and human IT resources on company performance driven by innovation and explore how IT infrastructure can be aligned strategically to improve organizational competitiveness and agility in an innovation-oriented business environment. The research method used in this study is qualitative interpretive research. The results revealed that companies with optimized IT infrastructure are more agile, efficient, and capable of transforming innovation into performance outcomes.

Yulianti et al (2024) conducted a study on the role of internal control systems (ICS) and good corporate governance (GCG) in fraud prevention efforts in organizational settings in Southeast Asian corporate environments. The study aims to explore how internal control systems function as tools for detecting and preventing fraud, examine the interrelationship between GCG practices (such as board oversight, transparency, and accountability), and the effectiveness of internal controls, and identify best practices and frameworks that integrate ICS and GCG for mitigating organizational fraud risks in Southeast Asian corporate environments. The study utilized a systematic literature review. The results revealed that strong internal control systems significantly reduce opportunities for fraud, particularly when aligned with clear governance policies.

3. Methodology

This section presents the methodology adopted for the study, outlining the procedures used to examine the effect of automated accounting systems on corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigates the effect of Information Technology Infrastructure and Internal Controls as components of automated accounting systems on financial performance. A descriptive research design was employed, as it is appropriate for examining the current state, practices, and impact of automated accounting systems within corporate entities without manipulating variables. This approach allows for a detailed assessment of the relationship between technological and control mechanisms within accounting systems and their influence on financial outcomes. Primary data was gathered through the administration of structured questionnaires distributed to finance managers, internal auditors, and IT officers across selected corporate organizations operating in South East Nigeria.

The questionnaire covered areas including the availability and quality of IT infrastructure, the robustness of internal control mechanisms, and their perceived or measurable impact on financial performance indicators such as profitability, return on assets, and operational efficiency. To ensure broad and unbiased representation, a stratified random sampling technique was adopted. The target population (N = 1,034) comprised three distinct professional groups: Finance Managers (FM) – 500 (48.4%), IT Professionals (ITP) – 300 (29.0%), and Internal Auditors (IA) – 234 (22.6%). Using Cochran's formula for determining sample size in a finite population, an initial sample of 384 was computed, which was adjusted to a final sample size of n = 288 respondents, with a valid return rate of

$n = 280$ (97.2%). Proportional allocation was used to distribute the sample across the three strata using the formula;

$$n_h = \left(\frac{N_h * n}{N} \right)$$

where n_h is the sample size for each stratum, N_h is the stratum population size, and N is the total population. Accordingly, 135 Finance Managers, 81 IT Professionals, and 64 Internal Auditors were selected. This stratification ensures that each professional group is proportionately represented, thereby enhancing the reliability and generalizability of the study's findings.

To assess the reliability of the research instrument, the test-retest method was applied. Questionnaires were administered, retrieved, and later re-administered to a subset of respondents to evaluate consistency in responses. Furthermore, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, ensuring that the measurement items reliably captured the constructs of interest. For data analysis, both descriptive statistics (such as percentages and frequency distributions) and inferential statistics (notably Chi-square tests) were used. These techniques facilitated the testing of the study's hypotheses regarding the impact of Information Technology Infrastructure and Internal Controls on corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria.

4. Result and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics

The demographic characteristics of the 280 respondents provide a robust foundation for analyzing the effect of automated accounting systems on corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria. The sample comprises 65% male and 35% female respondents, reflecting the higher male representation commonly observed in finance and IT-related roles, while ensuring adequate female participation in internal control and administrative accounting functions. In terms of age distribution, the majority of respondents (55%) fall within the 30–45 age group, representing mid-career professionals with considerable experience in accounting, financial management, and IT systems. Early-career professionals aged 20–29 constitute 25% of the sample, contributing fresh insights into modern digital accounting practices. The remaining 20% are aged above 45, capturing senior-level personnel such as financial controllers, auditors, and decision-makers with long-standing institutional experience. Regarding educational qualifications, 60% of respondents hold a Bachelor's degree, indicating a strong foundational academic background in accounting, finance, or information technology.

An additional 30% possess a Master's degree, reflecting advanced knowledge and strategic insight into corporate financial systems. The remaining 10% have obtained professional certifications in accounting, auditing, or IT governance such as ICAN, ACCA, or CISA further enhancing the credibility of the sample. In terms of work experience, 40% of respondents have 6–10 years of professional

experience, suggesting a mature understanding of both manual and automated accounting processes. 35% have 11–20 years of experience, offering deep institutional knowledge and operational insights. The remaining 25% have 1–5 years of experience, representing early adopters of contemporary automated financial systems and digital transformation initiatives. The respondents are drawn from diverse organizational categories to ensure a balanced perspective on automated accounting system implementation. 50% are employed in private corporate organizations, particularly in sectors like manufacturing, banking, and telecoms where digital accounting is prominent. 30% are from public sector institutions and government-owned enterprises, where financial control and automation are gaining policy attention.

The remaining 20% are from non-governmental and not-for-profit organizations, providing insights into accountability practices within third-sector financial systems. Notably, 70% of respondents reported that their organizations have already implemented at least one component of an automated accounting system, such as enterprise resource planning (ERP), digital auditing tools, or real-time financial reporting platforms. Conversely, 30% are at various pre-implementation or transitional stages, providing valuable perspectives on the challenges and readiness factors affecting full-scale automation in financial management.

Reliability Test

Testing the questionnaire reliability data was the first step undertaken to ensure appropriate analysis of the quantitative outcome. In this stage, one test was applied, namely, Cronbach’s alpha test. By conducting this test, the analysis moves to step 2 in which the most appropriate statistical tests were carried out.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Variable		Cronbach’s Alpha	Cronbach’s based on standardized Items	Alpha on
Information Technology		0.745	0.779	
Infrastructure				
Internal Controls		0.789	0.757	
corporate performance	financial	0.826	0.738	

Table 1 presents the reliability statistics of the research instrument, using Cronbach’s Alpha to assess the internal consistency of the measurement items for each variable. A Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.70 or higher is generally considered acceptable for social science research, indicating that the items within each scale reliably measure the underlying construct. The variable Information Technology

Infrastructure recorded a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.745 and 0.779 based on standardized items, suggesting a good level of internal consistency. Internal Controls showed an even higher reliability coefficient, with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.789 and 0.757 based on standardized items. This reflects strong internal consistency among items relating to control mechanisms. Finally, the variable Corporate Financial Performance yielded the highest reliability scores, with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.826 and 0.738 based on standardized items.

In summary, all three variables exhibit acceptable to high levels of internal consistency, indicating that the instrument is statistically reliable and suitable for further analysis in assessing the impact of automated accounting systems on corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria.

Table 2: Descriptive Summary

	Variables	N	Mean	Std.Dev
1	Information Technology Infrastructure	280	4.003	0.471
2	Internal Controls	280	4.214	0.424
3	corporate financial performance	280	3.861	0.453
	Aggregate Mean		4.026	0.449

Source: SPSS 28.0 Output

Table 2 provides a summary of the descriptive statistics for the major variables examined in this study: Information Technology Infrastructure, Internal Controls, and Corporate Financial Performance. The analysis is based on responses from 280 participants, with each construct assessed using a five-point Likert scale. The variable Internal Controls recorded the highest mean score of 4.214 with a standard deviation of 0.424. This suggests that respondents generally agree that robust internal control mechanisms are in place within their organizations. The high mean also indicates a strong perception of internal controls as a critical component of automated accounting systems contributing positively to financial performance. The relatively low standard deviation implies a high level of agreement among respondents. Information Technology Infrastructure yielded a mean score of 4.003 and a standard deviation of 0.471.

This indicates that the majority of respondents perceive their organizations to have well-established IT infrastructure supporting automated accounting processes. The closeness of the mean to the upper end of the Likert scale suggests a favorable evaluation of IT systems, though with slightly more variation in responses than internal controls. The variable Corporate Financial Performance recorded a mean of 3.861 and a standard deviation of 0.453. While slightly lower than the other two variables, this value still reflects a generally positive assessment of financial outcomes such as profitability, operational efficiency, and return on investment. The consistency of responses, as shown by the standard deviation, supports the reliability of this finding. In summary, the descriptive results suggest that organizations

in South East Nigeria have made significant strides in implementing automated accounting systems, particularly in strengthening internal controls and IT infrastructure.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis one

H₁: Information Technology Infrastructure has no significant effect on the corporate financial performance in south east Nigeria.

Table 3: Information Technology Infrastructure vs corporate financial performance

Hypothesis	Chi-Square	Degrees of freedom	P-value	Decision
Information Technology Infrastructure vs corporate financial performance	18.49	2	0.001	Fail to Accept H ₀

Source: SPSS 28.0 Output

Interpretation and decision

The Chi-Square test results in table 3 indicate that the p-value (0.001) is greater than the significance level (0.05). This means we fail to accept the null hypothesis (H₀), suggesting that there is a statistically significant effect of information technology on the corporate financial performance in south east Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H₁: Internal Controls has no significant effect on the corporate financial performance in south east Nigeria.

Table 4: Internal Controls vs corporate financial performance

Hypothesis	Chi-Square	Degrees of freedom	P-value	Decision
Internal Controls vs corporate financial performance	41.64	2	0.000	Reject H ₀

Source: SPSS 28.0 Output

Interpretation and decision

The Chi-Square test results in table 4 indicate that the p-value (0.000) is far below the significance level (0.05). This means we reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and conclude that internal control has a significant effect on the corporate financial performance in south east Nigeria.

Discussion of findings

This study was undertaken to examine the effect of Automated Accounting Systems (AAS) on Corporate Financial Performance (CFP) in South East Nigeria, with a specific focus on two critical components: Information Technology Infrastructure and Internal Controls. The findings provide empirical support for the hypothesized relationships and offer important insights into the practical and strategic significance of AAS in contemporary financial management. The reliability analysis confirmed that the measurement items used to assess the three major constructs Information Technology Infrastructure, Internal Controls, and Corporate Financial Performance—were internally consistent. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values ranged from 0.745 to 0.826, which exceeds the widely accepted threshold of 0.70 for social science research. This implies that the instrument was dependable for measuring the underlying constructs and suitable for the subsequent analysis. The reliability of the instruments ensures that the conclusions drawn from the study are both credible and replicable.

Descriptive statistics revealed generally high mean scores across all the study variables, indicating a favorable perception of AAS components and their influence on financial performance. Internal Controls had the highest mean value ($M = 4.214$, $SD = 0.424$), suggesting that respondents strongly believe in the effectiveness and importance of control mechanisms in ensuring financial accuracy, transparency, and accountability. This finding underscores the essential role internal controls play in safeguarding assets, preventing fraud, and maintaining compliance with financial regulations. Information Technology Infrastructure also showed a high mean ($M = 4.003$, $SD = 0.471$), suggesting that most organizations in the study area have adopted or are in the process of adopting robust IT systems to support financial operations. This includes the use of enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems, cloud accounting software, and automated reporting tools. Such infrastructure plays a crucial role in enhancing the speed, accuracy, and efficiency of financial transactions and reporting. Corporate Financial Performance had a slightly lower, yet still positive, mean score ($M = 3.861$, $SD = 0.453$), reflecting respondents' recognition of the benefits of AAS in improving profitability, return on investment, cost control, and financial transparency.

The first hypothesis tested the significance of the relationship between Information Technology Infrastructure and Corporate Financial Performance. The result of the Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 18.49$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.001$) revealed a statistically significant relationship, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that organizations with more advanced and integrated IT infrastructure experience better financial performance. (As you write this discussion kindly link it up with current literatures). The second hypothesis examined the relationship between Internal Controls and Corporate Financial Performance. The Chi-square test yielded a value of $\chi^2 = 41.64$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.000$, indicating a highly significant relationship. The null hypothesis was rejected, supporting the proposition that

strong internal control systems significantly influence financial outcomes. (As you write this discussion kindly link it up with current literatures)

5. Conclusion

The implementation of automated accounting systems in South East Nigeria has demonstrated a profound impact on corporate financial performance. As highlighted, the role of Information Technology Infrastructure is crucial; it not only enhances the efficiency of financial reporting but also facilitates timely decision-making, ultimately contributing to improved profitability and operational effectiveness.

Furthermore, the presence of robust internal controls within these automated systems ensures accuracy and reliability in financial data, which is essential for maintaining stakeholder trust and compliance with regulatory standards. This synergy between technology and internal controls creates a solid foundation for organizations, allowing them to navigate the complexities of the financial landscape with greater agility.

In conclusion, the integration of automated accounting systems, bolstered by effective IT infrastructure and internal controls, is instrumental in driving corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria. Organizations that embrace these technologies are likely to see enhanced financial outcomes, increased competitiveness, and sustainable growth in the dynamic business environment. The study concludes that Automated Accounting System has significant effect on the corporate financial performance in South East Nigeria.

Recommendations

- i. Organizations in South East Nigeria should prioritize investments in robust IT infrastructure. This includes upgrading hardware, software, and network systems to ensure seamless integration and operation of automated accounting systems. Improved IT infrastructure will enhance data processing capabilities, leading to better financial performance.
- ii. Organizations must implement and regularly review internal control mechanisms within their automated accounting systems. This includes establishing clear protocols for data entry, reconciliation, and reporting to minimize errors and fraud. A strong internal control framework will help maintain the integrity of financial data, thereby boosting stakeholder confidence.

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